

DAMAGE PROGRESSION IN COMPOSITE PRODUCTION RISER UNDER COMBINED LOADS

Won K. Kim and Ozden O. Ochoa*

*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Texas A&M University
3123 TAMU, College Station, TX 77840-3123, United States*

SUMMARY: The objective of this study is to investigate damage initiation and progression in a composite riser. Two separate analyses are performed to accomplish a detailed analysis of such a large structure without relying on extensive computations. First, a global static finite element analysis of the composite riser under combined loads is performed. Once the global analysis determines approximate location where damage is most likely to occur, a more detailed local analysis follows the global analysis. The local model of the expected damage region is created using shell elements. The local model applies a failure criterion to the individual layers of each element and identifies the damage modes. The local analysis shows that composite riser section is not likely to experience damage under the loads given by the global analysis. As the loads increase matrix cracking takes place in some layers, and with further increase in the loads fiber failure in tension eventually occurs.

KEYWORDS: riser, damage, static, finite element analysis, offshore production

INTRODUCTION

As offshore exploration and activities move into ultra deep water, composite materials are gaining more attention as promising substitutes for conventional steel and titanium. Top tensioned production systems, such as Tension Leg Platform (TLP) and Spar, are economically favorable for deep water production due to the vertical access to wells, however they are generally sensitive to payload increases. The use of composite materials in these structures is economically attractive due to their high specific stiffness and strength. Although metallic risers are lower in initial cost, they become more expensive in deep water due to their heavier weight and tensioner requirements. A viable application for composites in offshore structures is in production risers, which transport oil and/or gas from a wellhead to a surface production facility. Studies revealed that replacing all the metallic riser joints with equivalent composite joints results in a payload reduction of 2891 kN (650 kips), which realizes a cost savings of \$2.6MM to \$4.6MM [1]. In addition to the weight savings, composite materials provide excellent fatigue properties, corrosion resistance, and thermal (insulation) properties.

The main structural parts of a TLP system generally are comprised of floating vessel, riser, tensioner joint, bottom joint, and tethers. The riser is a string of mechanically connected segments. Each joint is typically 18m (60 ft) long. The bottom joint may be either a ball joint or a stress joint. The tensioner joint is a telescopic joint which transmits top tension to the riser from tensioner assemblies on the deck. The top tension controls the deflection of the

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of the riser, the section of interest is the one that undergoes the most severe combined loading effect. Several well-known failure criteria exist to assess damage [8-10]. The maximum strain criteria, for its simplicity, is incorporated in the local damage analysis of this study to track damage initiation and possibly progression of local redistribution.

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Deleted: Generally, for cross-ply laminates subject to axial loading, matrix cracking in the off-axis layers takes place first, followed by fiber fracture in the axial layers. The same phenomenon is expected in the riser analysis since the composite riser consists of alternating groups of axial and hoop layers. This study focuses on the identification of damage modes and the estimation of damage initiation and propagation. It is assumed that delaminations do not occur due to the cylindrical geometry of the object.

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GLOBAL RISER ANALYSIS

The global static analysis performed in this study is based on a typical platform that may be installed at 1829 m (6000 ft) water depth in Gulf of Mexico. Fig. 1 shows the configuration of the riser analyzed in this study simulating a 100 year hurricane condition. The loads applied to the system include top tension, representative weights, and current drag. The current velocity and the platform offset are assumed to be in the same direction, and thus the analysis is conducted as a 2-D problem. The effective moduli of the composite riser, including the liner, are calculated based on the classical laminate theory and incorporated into the model.

Fig. 1: Riser Configuration (not to scale) [11]

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Loads / Geometry

The composite riser joints are utilized from 35 m (116 ft) to 1825 m (5988 ft) elevations. Table 2 shows the impact of the composite riser on the weight reduction of the entire system by comparing the sum of the effective weights of all the joints, from the foundation casing to the tensioner joint, and the tensioner requirements with those of the equivalent steel riser. The current drag is simulated with a linear current profile, ranging from 0.06 m/s (0.2 ft/s) at the sea floor to 1.2 m/s (4.0 ft/s) at the surface [11]. Although the horizontal wave velocity is not included in the analysis, the TLP static offset is assumed to be 110 m (360 ft) based on a significant wave height of 12.5 m (41 ft) to represent the storm condition [11,12].

Table 2: Weight Comparisons between Steel Riser System and Composite Riser System

	Steel	Composite
Total Effective Wt.	2851 kN (641 kips)	609 kN (137 kips)

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Tensioner Requirements

3830 kN (861 kips)

881 kN (198 kips)

FEA Representation

The riser system is analyzed through ABAQUS finite element analysis software. Its Aqua module is for assigning current, wave, and wind loads to submerged or partially submerged structures [13]. The input to Aqua module are the current profile, ρ , C_D , and D . Then the current drag is evaluated with Eqn. 2 as a distributed load. The riser structure is modeled utilizing B21H beam element, which is a 2 node linear, shear flexible beam in a plane with hybrid formulation. Each node has three degrees of freedom, two translations and one rotation. Available output variables include axial stress, axial and transverse strains, curvature change, axial and transverse shear forces, and bending moment. Hybrid formulation, often used for modeling long pipes, includes axial and transverse shear forces as primary variables and prevents slight differences in nodal positions from causing large forces. A total of 631 beam elements, 587 of which constitute the composite riser part, are used in the analysis. Typically an element for the composite riser is 10 ft long, except for the transition regions from and to the steel joints where the mesh is refined. To account for the large displacements, non-linear geometry option is used. The displacements boundary conditions are clamped at the bottom of the foundation casing and the horizontal static offset at the tensioner centralizer.

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Analysis Results

As expected, the axial tension of the riser increases with elevation. The bending moment, on the other hand, remains relatively small throughout except at the riser extremities [12,14]. The axial tension and bending moment profiles are presented in Fig. 2. The composite riser experiences a maximum of 700kN (157 kips) of axial tension whereas the equivalent steel riser system experiences a maximum of 3650 kN (820 kips), representing a decrease of 80%. This is due to the weight reduction and the accompanying decrease in the top tension. Also, the bending moment that the stress joint experiences reduces by 45%, potentially enabling the redesigning and downsizing of the stress joint. The maximum bending moment of the entire system, 738 kN·m (544 kips·ft), occurs at the foundation casing, whereas the bottom of the stress joint experiences 488 kN·m (360 kips·ft).

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direction does not immediately follow the matrix cracking, and the first occurrence is seen at 14.0 times in outer layers, as seen in Fig. 4(b). Fiber fracture propagates at a slower rate than matrix cracking in the hoop layers.

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Fig. 3: Example of Damage Propagation – Matrix Cracking in the Outermost Hoop Layer (a) 7.5 times (b) 10.0 times

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Fig. 4: Expansion of Damage Areas (a) Hoop Layers - Matrix Cracking in Tension (b) Axial Layers - Fiber Fracture in Tension

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CONCLUSIONS

When most steel riser joints are replaced by composite riser joints, a significant reduction in weight can be expected, which will lead to downsizing of other parts such as the tensioner assembly and the stress joint. The reduction in the tensioner requirements is as much as 77% and the bending moment applied to the stress joint decreases by 45%. Due to the increasing

tension with elevation from the sea bed along with relatively small contribution of bending moment, the most severely stressed location in the composite riser is expected to be near the very top. However, as seen from the local damage analysis, no form of damage is observed at storm condition in the composite riser body. When the load magnitudes are multiplied, matrix cracking initiates in outer hoop layers first as a combined result of the applied tension and bending moment. Fiber fracture in the axial layers takes place much later than the initiation of matrix cracking, which almost coincides with the beginning of the deceleration of matrix cracking, and it propagates at a slower rate.

Although the bottom of the riser is subject to much less severe combined loading effect due to small axial tension, the bottom part is under higher hydrostatic external pressure. A combination of small axial tension, high external pressure, and bending moment may easily lead to buckling. While it was mainly the axial layers that maintained the structural integrity of the top, in the case of the bottom the hoop layers will play a major part. Currently efforts are focused on the buckling analysis under hydrostatic pressure and dynamic/fatigue analysis in which material degradation and long-term material properties [16,17] are taken into consideration.

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A global analysis utilizing shell or solid elements would be computationally intense due to the large scale of the structure.

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Total Effective Wt.		Tensioner Requirements	
Steel	Composite	Steel	Composite
2851 kN (641 kips)	609 kN (137 kips)	3830 kN (861 kips)	881 kN (198 kips)

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Fig. 2: Axial Tension and Bending Moment Profiles

COMPOSITE RISER SECTION STUDY

FE Model

The particular section “A” as identified to be critical from the global analysis is now modeled with shell elements, to which the material properties and the orientations are assigned on a layer-by-layer basis. S8R elements, eight-noded (reduced integration) thick

shell where transverse shear stiffness taken into account [13], are used. Each node has six degrees of freedom, three translations and three rotations. A total of 1600 elements, 20 circumferentially and 80 longitudinally, comprise this local model. Again, the non-linear geometry option is used. The three nodal degrees of freedom from the global analysis are applied as boundary conditions to each end of this 3 m-long cylindrical shell over multiple increments. It is assumed that the nodes at the ends have zero relative radial displacement with respect to the center. Also, all the nodes on each boundary is bound to a reference node located at the center, and therefore, the edge translates and rotates as a rigid body. For the damage analysis t

Also, the subroutine defines the local stiffness matrix and returns the state of stress, where a state of plane stress is assumed, and the reduced stiffness matrix is used.